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Preparation and evaluation of ibuprofen in-situ periodontal gel

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ABSTRACT

Periodontitis is a chronic inflammatory disease affecting supporting tissues of teeth. Conventional treatment is the systemic administration of antibiotics which requires repeated dosing and resulted in toxic adverse effects. These consequences can be solved by delivering the drug at the desired target site to show local therapeutic action. In situ gel-forming systems are polymeric system that exists as flowing solution before administration and undergoes phase transition to form a viscoelastic gel in a physiologic environment. Aim of the present work was to formulate and evaluate an in situ gelling drug delivery system of ibuprofen by using the polymers Polycaprolactone and Dichloromethane. The prepared in situ gels were evaluated for surface pH, viscosity, syringeability, gelation temperature, gelling time, in vitro gelling capacity, drug content and in vitro drug release. The formulation F3 was selected as the optimized formulation which has a gelation temperature of $36.33 \pm 0.57^\circ\text{C}$ with drug content of 84% and showed in vitro drug release of 95.45% at the end of 96 hrs. It follows first order release kinetics with Higuchi model drug release mechanism. The selected formulation was evaluated for its antibacterial activity and stable over three months.

Keywords: In situ, Periodontitis, Polycaprolactone, Ibuprofen, Dichloromethane and Release studies.

INTRODUCTION

The term periodontal diseases usually refers to common inflammatory disorders of gingivitis and Periodontitis that are caused by pathogenic micro flora in the bio film or dental plaque that forms adjacent to the teeth daily basis [1]. Periodontal diseases are localized inflammatory response due to infection of a periodontal pockets arising from the accumulation of sub gingival plaque. Clinical feature of Periodontitis include bleeding, pus discharge, halitosis, tooth mobility, functional impairment and ultimately tooth loss. The standard clinical measure for Periodontitis is bleeding on probing, clinical attachment level and depth pocket

depth [2]. Untreated Periodontitis results in the loss of the supporting structure of the tooth through resumption of alveolar bone and loss of periodontal ligaments attachment. Periodontal diseases therapy has been directed at altering the periodontal environmental to one, which is less conducive to the retention of bacterial plaque in vicinity of gingival tissue. Active phase of the diseases can be reversed dramatically by reducing the plaque levels. Topical administration of antibacterial agents in the form of mouth washes, dentifrices or gels can be used effectively in controlling supra gingival plaque [3, 4].

Ibuprofen is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) used for relieving pain, helping with fever and reducing inflammation. Ibuprofen work by inhibiting the enzyme cycle (COX), which converts arachidonic acid to prostaglandin H₂ (PGH₂). PGH₂, in turn, is converted by other enzymes to several other prostaglandins (which are mediators of pain, inflammation and fever) and to thromboxane A₂ (which stimulates platelet aggregation, leading to the formation of blood clots) [5].

In-Situ gelling systems improve the drug resistance time in periodontal pockets for effective treatment at the site of action. The technique (Sol-Gel transformed system) includes the use of novel formulations allowing drugs to be delivered in a controlled manner over a prolonged period of time. Hydro gels are polymeric networks that absorb large quantities of water while remaining insoluble in aqueous solutions due to chemical or physical cross linking of individual polymer chains [6]. They resemble natural living tissue more than any other class of synthetic biomaterials due to their high water content; furthermore, the high water content of the materials contributes to their biocompatibility. Hydro gels show minimal tendency to adsorb proteins from body fluids because of their low interfacial tension. Further, the ability of molecules of different sizes to diffuse into (drug loading) and out of (drug release) hydro gels allows the possible use of dry or swollen polymeric networks as drug delivery systems for oral, nasal, buccal, rectal, vaginal, ocular and parenteral routes of administration [7].

These polymers are endowed with an ability to swell in water or aqueous solvents and induce a liquid-gel transition. Currently, two groups of

hydro gels are distinguished namely preformed and in-situ forming gels. Preformed hydro gels can be defined as simple viscous solutions which do not undergo any modifications after administration. The use of preformed hydro gels still has drawbacks that can limit their interest for periodontal drug delivery or as tear substitutes [8-10].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ibuprofen, Polycaprolactone (PCL) and Dichloromethane (DCM) were obtained from SARC Research Labs Hyderabad.

Preformulation Study of Drug

Calibration curve of Ibuprofen

Accurately 100 mg of pure drug was weighed using electronic balance and it was dissolved in 100ml of methanol. The stock solution was kept for 30 mins and the solution was then filtered. From this stock solution 1ml of solution was taken and it was diluted with phosphate buffer pH 6.8 up to 100ml. Absorbance study of this final solution was carried out by using UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1700, Japan), within the wavelength region of 200 nm to 400 nm.

Compatibility studies by Fourier transformed infra-red spectroscopy

During gelatin process, the nature of interacting forces can be evaluated using this technique by employing potassium bromide pellet method [11].

Formulation Design

Total three formulations were prepared.

Table 1: Formulation of In-situ gel

Formulations	Ibuprofen	PCL	DCM
F ₁	10%	12.5%	87.5%
F ₂	10%	25%	75%
F ₃	10%	50%	50%

Method of preparation of In-situ gels

Take 5ml glass vials with proper airtight polypropylene caps. Appropriate amounts of polymer and solvent were weighed into glass vials. After initial mixing of the contents, vials were placed aside with occasional shaking overnight at room temperature to completely dissolve the

polymer. Weigh accurately finely powdered drug and add to above solution, close the lid and shake well and keep aside with occasional shaking and store in refrigerator at 8°C.

Characterization of prepared In-situ gels

Sol-Gel transition temperature and gelling time

Sol-gel transition temperature may be defined as that temperature at which the phase transition from sol meniscus to gel meniscus is occurred. Gel formation is indicated by a lack of movement of meniscus on tilting the tube. Gelling time is the time for first detection of gelation [12].

Surface pH of the gel

The PH of the gel was determined using a calibrated pH meter. The readings were taken for average of 3 samples.

Estimation of drug content in formulated gels

The prepared formulations were analyzed for the drug content by taking 1 ml of the smart gel in 50 ml volumetric flasks, 3ml of 6.8pH buffer was added and shaken to dissolve the drug, the volume was made up to the mark by 6.8pH buffer and the solution was left overnight. The drug content was determined by measuring the absorbance at 246 nm using UV-Visible spectrophotometer [13].

Viscosity of Gel

This is an important parameter for the in situ gels, to be evaluated. Viscosity and rheological properties of in situ forming drug delivery systems may be assessed using Brookfield rheometer or some other type of viscometers such as Ostwald's viscometer [14].

Syringeability

All prepared formulations were transferred into a 5 ml syringe placed with 20 gauge needle to a constant volume (2 ml). The solutions which were easily passed from syringe was termed as pass and difficult to pass were termed as fail [15].

In vitro drug release studies

Transfer 1ml simulated gingival fluid (6.8 phosphate buffer) into 5ml vials with cap. Inject using 1ml disposal syringes with #18 gauge known volume of formulation and see that gels are formed

or not. Drug release studies are conducted at specified time intervals of 1hr, 2, 4, 8, 12hrs and then 2, 4, 6, 8, 12, 16, 20, 24, 30 day intervals. Or every day after 24hrs ... until the entire drug is released from the formulation. Change the dissolution fluid totally by slowly drawing the fluid and replacing the container with 1ml of fresh dissolution fluid [16].

Release kinetics

To apprehend the drug release kinetics of the ibuprofen in situ gel formulation, the drug release data were treated with zero order, first order kinetics and Higuchi equation. The release mechanism was understood by fitting the data to Korsmeyer-peppas equation $M_t/M_\infty = Kt^n$, where M_t/M_∞ is fraction of drug released at time 't', 'K' is kinetic constant and 'n' is release exponent which characterized the drug release mechanism. If the value of 'n' is less than 0.45 then it is considered as Fickian release, values more than 0.45 and less than 0.89 is considered as anomalous (non-Fickian) transport and finally 'n' value greater than 0.89 follows super case-II release mechanism [17, 18].

FTIR Study for Optimized formulation

The optimized formulation evaluated using this technique by employing potassium bromide pellet method.

Stability study

Stability study of optimized formulation was carried out at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}/60 \pm 5\%$ and $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}/75 \pm 5\%$ RH for a period of three months. During stability study in situ gel was analyzed for pH, viscosity, drug content and in vitro drug release [19].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Calibration curve of Ibuprofen

The pure drug is scanned by UV-visible spectroscopy in between the range of 200-400nm, and the highest peak is observed at 224.5nm for Ibuprofen by using phosphate buffer at (6.8PH).

Table 2: Standard calibration graph of Ibuprofen

Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance
2	0.1004
4	0.1580
6	0.2407
8	0.3241
10	0.3732

Figure No.1: Standard calibration curve of Ibuprofen in pH 6.8 Phosphate buffer

The wave length of ibuprofen is 224.5nm was scanned from the concentration range of 2,4,6,8,10 µg/ml. Standard calibration graph of ibuprofen in 6.8 Phosphate buffer was plotted by taking concentration Vs absorbance and a good correlation was observed. The R² value of Ibuprofen are respectively 0.9927.

Compatibility studies by Fourier transformed infra-red spectroscopy

The possible interaction between the drugs, polymer and the excipients used the formulation development of periodontal in situ gel which was studied by FTIR spectroscopy. The spectra indicated that there was no interaction between drugs, polymer and excipients as the peaks of the drugs, polymer and excipients were not coincided.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure No.2: FTIR of (a) Ibuprofen (b) Polycaprolactone (c) Mixture of both

Characterization of prepared In-situ gels

Sol-Gel transition temperature and gelling time

The sol- gel transition temperature of formulations is noted to find out their ability to form in situ gel inside the oral cavity. The gelation

temperature was found in the range of $33.33 \pm 1.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ – $36.33 \pm 0.57^{\circ}\text{C}$. The time required for the solution to form gel is recorded in seconds. The gelling time was found to increase with increasing concentration of Polycaprolactone. The gelation time was found to be in the range 56.33 ± 1.15 - 67 ± 1.52 seconds.

Table 3: Sol-Gel Transition Temperature and Gelling time of Ibuprofen *In Situ* gel

Formulation	Sol-Gel transition temperature	Gelling time
F1	33.33 ± 0.57	56.33 ± 1.15
F2	34.66 ± 0.57	59.66 ± 1.52
F3	36.33 ± 0.57	67 ± 1.52

Surface pH of the gel

The results of the surface pH value for all formulations. The values represent the mean of three replicates. The values of surface pH of all the gels observed were well within the range of neutral pH. This indicates that formulation can be used and will not cause any irritation in the oral cavity.

Estimation of drug content in formulated gels

Drug content uniformity was also performed to ensure minimum batch to batch variations. Table.No.4 show the values of drug content of formulated gels. Estimation of drug content in all the formulations was observed that shows fairly uniform drug content. This is because of easy and

single step preparation i.e., addition of drug to the polymer solution accounted for minimal or no drug loss.

Viscosity of Gel

Viscosity of gels was determined by using Brookfield Viscometer. The viscosity values in dyne/cm² are shown in Table. No 4. The viscosities of all gels values were found to be 323, 347, and 364 dynes/cm² for formulations F1 to F3 respectively which indicates that formulations containing more amount of polymer are more viscous than the formulation containing low amount of polymer.

Table 4: Showing Surface pH, Viscosity, Drug Content

Formulation Code	Surface Ph	Viscosity (dynes/cm ²)	Drug Content
F ₁	7.60	347	71%
F ₂	6.94	323	79%
F ₃	6.74	354	84%

Syringeability

The results of the Syringeability study indicate that all the gel formulations were syringeable through 22 gauge needle.

In vitro drug release studies

The percentage drug release of Ibuprofen in all formulations F₁, F₂, F₃, (60.85%), (62.54%), (95.45%).

Table 5: % Cum. of drug release of Formulations

Time(h)	% Cum. of drug release of Formulations		
	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃
0.083	3.64	3.65	3.65
0.166	6.35	5.01	8.09
0.333	7.91	7.8	9.55
0.5	12.02	10.47	11.75
1	15.49	15.69	17.46
2	19.91	27	24.53
4	36.17	42.47	38.76
6	45.26	48.3	45.63
8	48.22	49.3	59.88
10	52.47	50.54	71.62
12	53.57	51.27	73.5
48	55.65	54.62	85.74
72	59.7	59.78	89.95
96	60.85	62.54	95.45

Figure No.3: In Vitro drug release Studies

Drug release kinetics

The results of in vitro release data was plotted to various kinetic models in order to know the drug release mechanisms. The results drug release

kinetics of optimized formulation F3 showed that the drug release followed first order kinetics with Higuchi model drug release mechanism

Table 6: Release Kinetics of Ibuprofen In situ Gel

Formulation	Zero order	First Order	Higuchi	Korsmeyer Peppas	
				R ²	n
F1	0.784	0.981	0.929	0.921	0.711
F2	0.697	0.976	0.922	0.918	0.694
F3	0.798	0.988	0.954	0.928	0.659

FTIR Study for Optimized formulation

IR spectra of optimized formulation were observed which indicates that all the functional

groups are present hence which says that there are no interactions.

Figure No.4: FTIR Studies of F3 Formulation

Stability studies

The optimized formulation F3 was selected for short term stability. During stability study formulation F3 was analysed for pH, viscosity,

drug content and in vitro drug release and result showed no significant changes in any of these parameters. Thus, prepared formulation was stable throughout the study period.

Table 7: Stability studies of F3 Formulation

Time	At 25±2 °C/60±5%RH				At 40±2 °C/75±5% RH			
	pH	Viscosity (dynes/cm ²)	Drug Content	Invitro drug release	pH	Viscosity (dynes/cm ²)	Drug Content	Invitro drug release
Initial	6.74	354	84 %	95.45	6.74	354	84 %	95.45
1 month	6.73	352	83 %	95.10	6.72	352	83%	94.90

2 month	6.71	349	82.5 %	94.87	6.70	348	82 %	94.70
3 month	6.70	347	82 %	93.68	6.69	346	81.5 %	93.07

CONCLUSIONS

In this present study *in situ* gel of Ibuprofen for the treatment of periodontal diseases was successfully formulated using Polycaprolactone as gel base. This *in situ* gel formulation possesses mucoadhesive properties, results of which prolong residence time at the site of application, which in turn exhibited better effects. In addition, *in situ* gel provides intimate contact between the drug and the absorbing tissue which may result in high drug concentration in local area. Thus, based upon

obtained results it can be concluded that the formulation containing 50% Polycaprolactone and 50% Dichloromethane was considered as an optimized formulation and provided sustained drug release over an extended period of time i.e. more than 90% drug was released in 96 hr this may leads to better patient compliance. The prepared *in situ* gel containing ibuprofen can be an innovative and promising approach for the treatment of periodontal disease.

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